

Spinsterhood - Its Causes And Treatment In The Holy Quran: Contemporary Social Thematic Study

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: December 07, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: February 28, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Spinsterhood, treatment and Holy Quran</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4569146</p>	<p><i>Spinner in language the woman spins the spinster by joining spinsters and people, and Al-Asma`i said, "I was impassioned by what he did not name the perpetrator because she is whispering, and it was said that I missed, and the spinster among men and women who remain for a time after he realizes he does not marry. Most of what is used in women are said that the woman is spineless, because she is spinster, and impure, and she is stubborn if she grows up and is incapacitated. Idiomatically spinster: is the girl who resides with her family after reaching the age of marriage for a long time and she did not marry and knew her. Likewise, it is called a man who did not marry. The scholars differed regarding determining the age of a spinster, according to several statements, It was said that spinsterhood begins from the twenty-fifth, it was said that it was thirty years, and it was said thirty-three, and it was said that it was thirty-five, and it was said forty years, and it was said that it was forty-five to sixty years, and that difference in determining the age of spinsterhood is due to the prevailing custom in each region.</i></p>

Introduction

Praise be to Allah, Lord of the worlds, and prayers and peace be upon our master Muhammad and upon his family and companions as a whole...

And yet...

Dear brothers and sisters, our Islamic religion took care of the formation of the Muslim family, because it is the foundation of society, and our Prophet Muhammad, may Allah bless him and grant him peace, likened it to a compact Lebanon that tightens each other. Therefore, Islam put all solutions for the happiness of the Muslim family, but the reality of the family today is very deteriorating. This is because of the bad habits introduced by the variables of civilization, whose negative effects are reflected at all levels, especially social issues.¹

Among these variables is the spread (spinsterhood phenomenon) as well as within the responsibilities of the family, a large number of disability, the spread of drugs and suicide among young men and women, and other social phenomena. One of these phenomena that have caught my eye is the phenomenon of spinsterhood, which no sane person can ignore because women are half of society, and if we leave this half without care, the problem remains, which is the instability of the Islamic family.

Because of this importance in society, I studied it an objective Qur'anic study, so that I may have contributed to reducing the danger of this phenomenon to Islamic society after Islam came with several solutions to this phenomenon, so the title of my research was this (spinster _ and its causes _ and its treatment in the Holy Quran) is an objective study.²

The nature of the research required that it be from an introduction in which I explained the importance of the topic and an optional reason for it, and a preamble in which I explained the definition of spinsterhood, and four demands, which are as follows:

- The first requirement/causes of spinsterhood.
- The second requirement / solve the problem in the Holy Quran.
- The third requirement/judgment of pluralism and opinions of thinkers / divided it into two branches
- First / the wisdom of diversity
- Second / the opinions of Western thinkers about diversity
- Fourth requirement/statistics and questionnaire
- First / Proportion of Spouses and Widows in Iraq and Other Countries
- Second / Women's opinions on diversity through questionnaire forms

Then I followed up with a conclusion in which I outlined my most important findings and recommendations.

The age of spinsterhood:

The scholars differed on determining the age of the spinster to several sayings:

It was said that spinsterhood begins from the twenty-fifth, it was said thirty years and thirty-three, it was said thirty-five, and it was said forty years, and it was said forty-five to sixty years, and that difference in determining the age of spinster is due to the norm prevailing in each region.

4. Islam looked at all women with a fair and balanced view, and it was injected into marriage and did not differentiate between one woman and another. So what is the fault of spinsters and widows - it does not look at them with a look of sympathy and tenderness when they are in the coming of life.
5. Which is better for two wives to live under the care of one husband, or for a woman to live with a husband who has ten girlfriends or more or less.
6. The nature of a woman differs from a man in her willingness to have intercourse because of the menstrual cycle, unlike a man, who is ready for cohabitation throughout the year.
7. The wife may be sterile and not give birth, so the husband is deprived of the blessing of the child. Instead of divorcing her, he remains with her and marries the children.
8. The wife may get sick or her behaviour may be bad, so instead of divorcing her, he remains with her and marries another.
9. Marriage to the second wife brings comfort to the first wife, and this reduces her burden of serving the husband.
10. They petitioned for a reward from Allah Almighty, which is for a man to marry a poor woman or a widow without a breadwinner or shepherd, and he marries her with the intention of her chastity and care.¹²
 - Second / Opinions of Western thinkers on polygamy

The books and articles of Western thinkers have shown that there is a relationship between the prevention of polygamy and the high incidence of foundlings.

We will show some of them as follows:

- In the conference held by the French government in the year (1901AD) to search for the best ways to resist the spread of prostitution, they said: (The number of found fewer children gathered in the shelters of the "Seine" district alone reached (50,000) a foundling and their education is underway at the expense of the province.
- Rather, some of the employees of these shelters abhor the girls who come under their jurisdiction, but the same foundlings abhor some of them, and no grudging rebukes them.¹³ And an English writer wrote in this regard, where she said: "Our daughters have been absent from the misfortune, and the researchers have said about the reason for this, and as a woman, I look at these girls and my heart is broken with pity and grief for them.

What is this disease ...

Where is the disease ...

Then the scientist "Thomas" answered her because I see the disease and I have prescribed a medicine for her, which is the permissibility of men to marry more than one woman, and with this, the affliction will disappear and the girls become housewives. The calamity is all the calamity in forcing the European man to be satisfied with one wife, and with this determination he made the daughters homosexual and deviant... However, I would like to point out that polygamy was permitted in Christian Europe until the era of "Sharman", who was married to more than one woman Then priests urged those married to more than one wife to choose one from among the wives and divorce the second, and so was the word Church On our hands did they support?¹⁴

The same is the case in (Turkey) when I abandoned Islam and enacted the Western law in (1926 AD) that prohibits polygamy, and after eight years have passed, secret births proliferated, custom wives increased and the number of intercourse increased.¹⁵

Fourth requirement/statistics and questionnaire

And it divided into two branches

- First: The percentage of unmarried women and widows in Iraq, and some countries of the world issued by the Organization for Women's Rights in Iraq, which is an organization concerned with defending the rights of Iraqi women and publishes monthly reports periodically. In a report published on the Internet, it indicated:
 - That 19% of Iraqi women are between widows and spinsters. The report indicated that between (90-100) Iraqi women are widowed daily as a result of acts of sectarian violence and killings. The report also indicated that there are (300) thousand widows in Baghdad alone in addition to (8) millions widows in various countries. This means that the percentage of widows constitutes (35%) of the souls of Iraq (65%) of the number of Iraqi women (80%) of the number of married women.
 - The percentage of unmarried women in Iraq reached the highest rate in the Arab world, which is (85%) of Iraqi women, between spinsters and widows, until the end of 2006¹⁶. In addition to that, the Global Society magazine published issue (847) statistics on the ratios of males versus females in several world countries, which are as follows:

Table 1. Showthe ratio of males to females in several world countries

(3) females	(1) Male	Arab Gulf States
For (4) females	(1) Male	USA

- Islam Fatwa Question and Answer, compiled and verified by Abu Yusuf Al-Qahtani and Abu Omar Afallah, under the supervision of Muhammad Salih Al-Munajjid.
- In the Shadows of the Qur'an, Syed Qutb - Dar Al Shorouk.
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